

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Substituted Mandelic Acids by Ceric Ammonium Nitrate

KALYAN K. BANERJI

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur 342001

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The oxidation of mandelic acid and nine substituted mandelic acids by ceric ammonium nitrate has been studied. The oxidation involves an initial formation of a Ce(IV)—mandelic acid complex which decomposes in the rate-determining step. The formation constant of the complex is not much sensitive to polar substituents. The active oxidising species is Ce(OH)⁺. The induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile and the estimation of carbon dioxide produced indicated that the rate-determining step involves oxidative decarboxylation. The oxidation exhibits a reaction constant $\rho^+ = -1.10 \pm 0.06$ at 25°. The mechanistic conclusions are discussed.

OXIDATION of alcohols and diols by cerium (IV) salts has been widely studied¹. It has been found that the mechanism of the oxidation of diols depends on the nature of the Ce(IV) salts used. With Ce(IV) perchlorate and nitrate the Micheales-Menton type kinetics has been observed whereas Ce(IV) sulphate yields simple second order kinetics². The oxidation of α -hydroxy acid by Ce(IV) has been reported by several investigators³. Grover and Gupta⁴ suggested that the oxidation of substituted glycollic acids by cerium (IV) sulphate takes place via complex formation, though no kinetic evidence has been presented. No systematic study of the effect of structure on the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by cerium (IV) has been reported. The present communication reports the details of the oxidation of mandelic acid by ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) and evaluates the reaction constant.

Results

The oxidation of mandelic acid (0.1M) by CAN (0.01M) in 1.0M nitric acid, yields mainly benzaldehyde which can be isolated as its 2,4 dinitrophenylhydrazone in 95% yield. The measurements of carbon dioxide evolved indicated that the overall reaction can be represented as follows :

The oxidation of *p*-nitro- and *m*-bromo mandelic acids also give the corresponding benzaldehydes and carbon dioxide.

It is observed that in control experiments, with Ce(IV) absent, nitric acid is not reduced by the hydroxy acid, under the present experimental conditions.

Rate Laws : When the hydroxy acid is in excess, the disappearance of Ce(IV) follows first rate laws. At constant Ce(IV) concentration the rate of the

oxidation was found to increase with increase in the concentration of the hydroxy acid but the order is less than one (Table 1). The result suggests that the oxidation proceeds through the formation of a complex between the hydroxy acid and Ce(IV).

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF THE RATE WITH THE CONCENTRATION OF MANDELIC ACID

[Ce(IV)] 4.0 × 10 ⁻³ M, [HNO ₃] 1.0M, $\mu = 2.5$ Temp. 25°	5.0	10	15	20	25
10 ² [M.A.]M	5.0	10	15	20	25
10 ⁶ k ₁ s ⁻¹	3.75	6.70	8.52	11.0	12.8

The variation of the rate with the concentration of the hydroxy acid is given by the expression,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}(\text{IV})]}{dt} = \frac{ks[\text{Hydroxy acid}][\text{Ce}(\text{IV})]}{1/K + [\text{Hydroxy acid}]} \quad \dots (3)$$

The value of *K*, the formation constant of the complex, can be obtained from the plot of 1/*k*₁ against 1/[hydroxy acid]. The formation constants (*K*) for the substituted mandelic acid—Ce(IV) complex were determined at 25° by this method (Table 2).

Effect of Hydrogen ions : At constant ionic strength, increase in hydrogen ion concentration causes a slight but distinct decrease in the oxidation rate of mandelic acid. This is reminiscent of the effect

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE SUBSTITUTED MANDELIC ACID—CERIUM(IV) COMPLEX AT 25°

[HNO ₃] 1.0M		μ = 2.5				
Substituent	H	p-F	p-Cl	p-Br	p-Et	
K 1 mol ⁻¹	2.50	2.57	2.42	2.48	2.62	
Substituent	p-Me	p-OMe	m-Br	m-NO ₂	p-NO ₂	
K 1 mol ⁻¹	2.53	2.60	2.40	2.41	2.30	

observed by Mathur and Bakore⁵ and suggests that Ce(OH)³⁺ is the active oxidising species. The value of the hydrolysis constant, *K_h*, for the reaction (4)

was found to be 6.32 at 35° and this value is very close to one reported by Mathur and Bakore⁵.

Kinetic Isotope Effect: Kemp and Waters⁶ reported that the oxidation of α-deuteriomandelic acid by cerium (IV) sulphate indicated a *k_H/k_D* = 1.2 at 25°. The oxidation by CAN also results in negligible kinetic isotope effect, *k_H/k_D* = 1.07 at 25°.

Solvent Isotope Effect: The oxidation of mandelic acid was carried out in 95% deuterium oxide, and the rate constants in D₂O and H₂O, at 25° and [HNO₃] = 1.0M, are 10⁵ *k₁* = 3.61 and 3.71 s⁻¹ respectively. The solvent isotope effect is also nearly zero, confirming the earlier observation⁷ in the oxidation of pinacol by Ce(IV) sulphate.

Induced Polymerisation of Acrylonitrile: The oxidation of mandelic acid was carried out in presence of acrylonitrile in an oxygen free atmosphere. The reaction results in the formation of dense polymer. In control reactions, with the hydroxy acid absent, no polymer formation was observed. The amount of carbon dioxide evolved during the reaction was estimated (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ESTIMATION OF CARBON DIOXIDE FORMED DURING THE OXIDATION OF MANDELIC ACID BY CAN IN 1.0M HNO₃

[M.A.] M	[Ce(IV)] M	[Acrylonitrile] M	mol of CO ₂ / mol of Ce(IV)
0.05	0.01	—	0.48
0.1	0.01	—	0.50
0.1	0.01	0.02	0.67
0.1	0.01	0.03	0.73

Effect of Temperature: The rates of the oxidation of substituted mandelic acids were measured at different temperatures (Table 4). The apparent activation energy was obtained by plotting log *k₁* against inverse of absolute temperature. In the present reaction, the significance of activation energy is difficult to visualize as it is a combination of several reactions. The error limit in the value of activation energy is ±2.0 kcal mol⁻¹.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE REACTION RATE

Subs.	10 ⁵ <i>k₁</i> s ⁻¹				Δ <i>E</i> * kcal/mol
	20°	25°	35°	40°	
H	21.4	37.1	112	216	22.0
p-F	16.6	31.6	110	290	22.3
p-Cl	15.1	28.8	101	178	22.7
p-Br	13.2	25.8	91.3	166	23.0
p-Et	38.0	77.8	245	478	20.5
p-Me	40.7	81.3	257	484	20.0
p-OMe	158	262	708	1140	18.0
m-Br	7.1	14.1	50.0	95.5	23.5
m-NO ₂	4.2	8.3	31.0	57.5	24.0
p-NO ₂	2.55	5.25	20.4	39.0	24.5

Discussion

The data presented in Table 2 indicate that both electron donating and withdrawing substituents have very little effect on the stability of cerium (IV)—mandelic acid complex. This agrees with the observation of Young and Trahanovsky⁸ with benzyl alcohol—CAN system, and of Balasubramanian and Venkatasubramanian⁹ with benzyl alcohol—cerium (IV) perchlorate system. This small electronic effect is reasonable in view of the fact that at least five σ bond must separate the substituent from the metal. It should be noted that the equilibrium constants reported are "apparent" equilibrium constants since they represent the position of the equilibrium of all cerium (IV) species with the hydroxy acid to form a cerium (IV)—mandelic acid complex. However, as the conditions were kept constant for all the hydroxy acids; the cerium (IV) species should be same for all hydroxy acids.

The absence of kinetic isotope effect confirms that the α-C-H bond is not broken in the rate determining step. This also disapproves the earlier mechanism suggested for the oxidation of α-hydroxy acid¹.

The induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile indicates the formation of free radicals during the reaction. This is consistent with the one-electron oxidations by cerium (IV). The yield of carbon dioxide, in the presence of acrylonitrile, is increased rather than decreased (cf. Table 3). It thus becomes clear that carbon dioxide is formed directly and *via* a free radical. The rate-determining step is, therefore, a oxidative decarboxylation producing simultaneously a free radical. Thus a mechanism¹⁰ suggested earlier for mandelic acid—Ce(IV) perchlorate reaction is operative in this case also.

The rate of the oxidation of the ten mandelic acids correlate well with the Brown's σ^+ values¹¹ ($r = 0.993$) with a reaction constant $\rho^+ = -1.10 \pm 0.06$ at 25°. Thus the decomposition of the mandelic acid—cerium (IV) complex leading to the intermediate radical involves production of an electron-deficient transition state, albeit a weak one. The value of the reaction is in accord with the reaction constants in other radical reactions¹¹ which are normally between -0.5 and -1.5 .

Experimental

Materials : The preparation and specifications of the organic compounds used have been described earlier¹². All other chemicals used were analytical grade reagents. Nitric acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Kinetic Measurements : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first-order conditions by keeping a large excess of the hydroxy acid over cerium (IV). The ionic strength was kept constant at $\mu = 2.5M$ by using sodium nitrate. The temperature was kept constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The reaction vessels were painted black from outside.

The rate of the oxidation was followed by quenching aliquots in slight excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate and back titrating the residual Fe(II) with standardized cerium (IV) sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator. The rates were obtained by at least duplicate measurements and were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Carbon Dioxide Estimation : The yield of carbon dioxide was determined manometrically in a Warberg apparatus¹³ using fast green FCF dissolved in ethyl lactate as the manometric fluid.

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